

City of Motorcycles. Objective and subjective factors behind the rise of motorcycle mobility in Barcelona

Oriol Marquet
Carme Miralles-Guasch
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

Abstract:

In the past ten years, the number of motorbikes in Barcelona, Spain has grown to represent nearly one out of four vehicles in the city, making it now the highest two-wheeled motorisation rate of all European cities. In this study we explore the motorcycle phenomenon from a threefold perspective, following the temporal trend of this growth, seeking the sociodemographic profiles of its users, and assessing their subjective motivations that explain the use of this specific mode of transport. We first measure the impact of motorcycles along a 2004-2012 timeline that covers both pre- and post-crisis data. Secondly, logistic and multinomial regression models are implemented to analyse the drivers and significant predictors of motorbike ownership and modal choice. Finally, we compare how motorcyclists and car drivers rated their main use of transport and how they evaluated the inherent risk of riding and driving, respectively. They gave different patterns of answers when trying to justify their modal choice. The results highlight the importance of motorized two-wheeled modes of transport of the affordability factor to help understand the rise of this kind of transport, even in times of economic crisis. Overall, motorcycle use is explained by a set of objective on everyday mobility in compact and dense urban environments, and also stress the relevance and subjective factors that are seeking to resolve specific and unique motoring needs, and that is not equal to the set for car drivers.

Keywords: motorcycles; two-wheeled mobility; modal choice; Urban mobility; Barcelona

1. Introduction

In recent years, European cities have seen a dramatic increase in the number of motorized two-wheeled vehicles circulating through their streets. Although two-wheeled mobility is nothing new for many cities from developing countries, and it has already been high in some European Countries in the past (Nishitateno & Burke, 2014), the recent expansion of per capita motorcycle ownership throughout Europe has been unprecedented (Paviotti & Vogiatzis, 2012). Far from being thoroughly planned, the rise of motorbike mobility in some south European countries such as Greece, Italy and Spain, is shaping new mobile scenarios as well as brand new needs and challenges for authorities to cope with (Pinch & Reimer, 2012).

From the beginning, the two-wheeled motorized mobility expansion has been tolerated and has drawn complicity from local governments, as a cheap way to ease congestion in densely populated cities, at the same time that it solves the parking issue in the city centres (Albalate & Fernández-Villadangos, 2010). The growing number of motorcycle users however has also unveiled new problems. For once, switching from car to motorcycle can represent a perceived improvement for drivers, but it does not solve any of the environmental problems caused by motorised mobility. In fact, two-wheelers emit a little less CO₂ than regular tourisms while having lower occupancy rates (Ducreux, 2008) and, additionally, they are much more pollutant in terms of noise (Barbusse & Ducreux, 2005; Paviotti & Vogiatzis, 2012). A sudden rise in motorcycle use can also cause additional congestion (Truitt, 2008), especially when new motorcyclists are not switching from car use, but are coming from transit or non-motorised modes of transport. However, the most troubling aspect of the rise of two-wheeled mobility is its accident rate. Motorcycles are the most vulnerable mechanised mode of transport, as they lack a protective chassis and most security devices (Albalate & Fernández-Villadangos, 2010). Because of that, and as reported by Jevtić et al. (2015), 15% of total fatalities in the EU-24 in 2010 involved a two-wheeled motorized vehicle and out of those, 45% corresponded with accidents which occurred inside urban areas (Albalate & Fernández-Villadangos, 2009). Jamson and Chorlton (2009) observed that in the specific case of the UK, motorbike fatalities were 40 times higher than for cars.

Because of these worrisome figures, most of the recent academic literature involving motorbike mobility has been focused either on its environmental outcomes (Barbusse & Ducreux, 2005; Ducreux, 2008; Kumar, Durai, Saleh, & Boswell, 2011; Lin et al., 2008; Lumbreras, Valdés, Borge, & Rodríguez, 2008) or on road safety and accident analysis

(Albalade & Fernández-Villadangos, 2010; Chesham, Rutter, & Quine, 1993; Espié, Boubezoul, Aupetit, & Bouaziz, 2013; Jevtić et al., 2015; Olabarria, Perez, Santamarina-Rubio, Novoa, & Racioppi, 2012; Perez, Borrell, & Nebot, 2009).

But, the rise of two-wheeled mobility in dense and complex urban environments of Mediterranean cities, like Barcelona, requires broader analysis going beyond accidentality. In this context there is a surprising lack of studies addressing the phenomenon of motorbike mobility (Kopp, 2011). The most significant corpus of studies belong to South Asian countries (Chen & Lai, 2011; Jou, Wu, & Chen, 2011; Lin et al., 2008; Truitt, 2008; Yamamoto, 2009) although their conclusions are difficult to apply to European or Mediterranean urban realities. We still know very little of motorcyclist behaviour, their needs and motivations, and the underlying factors that are causing an ever-growing number of people to change their modal choice (Espié et al., 2013). This lack of thought on urban motorcycle use is even more striking when we compare it with the extensive literature on car driving, even when in some cities like Barcelona, there is now one motorcycle travel for every 2.7 trips made by car.

The literature now acknowledges that the use of private individual modes of transport like the car and potentially the motorbike, is determined by a large combination of factors (De Witte et al., 2013). Out of those, subjective and affective factors play a significant role (Mann & Abraham, 2006). Internal decisions and individual choices that trigger a specific modal choice, respond to instrumental factors such as travel time, speed and economic cost, but also to emotional and non-instrumental factors like symbolism, status or habit (Miralles-Guasch, Martinez-Melo, & Marquet Sarda, 2014; Steg, 2005). In addition, modal choice does not only depend on projected qualities of a specific mode of transport but also by the perceived inability of other modes of transport to meet the same qualities (Thøgersen, 2006). Most literature on modal choice takes into account both built environment characteristics, people's socioeconomic features and the character and potentials of each mode of transport. Because of the latter, factors affecting motorbike choice, are significantly different from that of public transport, and even that those affecting other private modes of transport such as the car. Despite that, there are also some factors that have been proved to affect car use that can also be related to the motorbike. Among those variables, the importance of vehicle ownership as a pre-requisite to move by car is equally applied to the motorbike. Existing literature has proven a strong relationship between socioeconomic variables

and vehicle ownership (Law, Hamid, & Goh, 2015), particularly with income levels, due to the high cost of the vehicle. Spatial characteristics of the built environment also affect both the decision of purchasing a vehicle and the afterwards modal choice decision (Santos, Maoh, Potoglou, & von Brunn, 2013). However, spatial and socioeconomic factors alone can't explain neither vehicle ownership nor vehicle use by themselves (Acker, Derudder, & Witlox, 2013) without taking also into account subjective variables and personal rationalities (Acker, Mokhtarian, & Witlox, 2011).

Despite the recent interest drawn by the subjective and symbolical factors associated with car use (Chen & Lai, 2011), symbolical and instrumental drivers of motorbike use still remain deeply unknown. It is to address these literature gaps that this paper sets out to answer which are the variables that better predict motorcycle ownership and use in Barcelona. In doing so, this paper also analyses some of the underlying and subjective aspects of motorcycle use.

2. Two-wheeled mobility and the dense city: Barcelona city of Motorcycles

The advantages of riding a motorcycle inside a dense and compact city with favourable weather conditions such as in Barcelona are numerous. The first and most evident is that it avoids most of the congestion that mainly affects car driving. Being able to manoeuvre between cars in traffic makes the driver immune to traffic jams and unexpected traffic congestion (Pinch & Reimer, 2012). Thus, the motorcycle allows not only faster speeds, but also eliminates costs in terms of time and inconvenience of having to find a parking spot. Thus, it provides a better anticipation of total travel times, as the motorcyclist is less dependent on optimal traffic conditions (Espíe et al., 2013). In one of the few papers that addresses motorcycle mobility in European cities, Kopp (2011) estimates that motorcycle travel times within the city of Paris are 49% shorter than car travel times. Lower travel times may also mean lower costs and most importantly, higher speeds enhance the driving experience (Broughton et al., 2009). Finally, the possibility of free and easy parking makes it even more attractive for the citizens of Barcelona to change their modal choice and to adopt motorcycling (Ballart & Riba, 1995).

However, the fact that Barcelona has become the European city with more motorcycles, ranking second only with respect to Rome, and the first one in terms of motorcycles per

inhabitant (Albalate & Fernández-Villadangos, 2010), cannot only be explained by operational factors. In the specific case of Barcelona, in 2004 the Spanish government enacted a regulatory measure that actually provided car drivers with a motorcycle license if they had been driving a car for a period of three years. The measure allowed veteran car drivers to switch to motorbikes with capacity up to 125 cc without any further examination or test (Perez et al., 2009). Many car drivers that were dissatisfied with driving conditions inside the city saw the opportunity to improve those conditions without having to completely abandon motorised private transport (Albalate & Fernández-Villadangos, 2010). Resulting from that policy change, that was mainly oriented to ease traffic congestion in the city centre, the number of motorcycles in Barcelona increased by an average of 7.5% annually from 2004 to 2007, with the majority of new users being, as we shall further see in the results section, middle-aged veteran drivers.

Also noteworthy is the fact that the rise in the number of motorcycles, which had its origin in a pre-crisis era, has continued even if it has slowed down slightly during the economic crisis that has deeply affected not only the income and purchasing power of families throughout Spain –Barcelona being no exception- but also their travel behaviour (Sobrino & Monzon, 2014). Studying the specific trend of motorcycle use before and after Spain's economic crisis of 2008, can broaden the issue of how the motorcycle relates with economic development, along with the income level of its users. On that specific context Nishitateno and Burke (2014) and Pinch and Reimer (2012) highlight that the affordability of the motorcycle, particularly in relation to the car, is a central factor in explaining the role and importance of motorbike mobility both at the local and the global scales.

3. Methodology

Design and study population

Our aim was to study the travel behaviour of motorcycle users in the city of Barcelona. It is a cross-sectional study that uses mobility data from two travel surveys taken in 2004 and 2012 for Barcelona residents above 16 years of age. For this study, we observed the everyday journeys reported by individuals living in Barcelona that had taken place inside the city. In order to analyse mobility patterns that took place in a

common built environment, only trips that had an origin and a destination inside the municipality of Barcelona were included.

Data sources

The main data sources were the EMEF 2004 and EMEF 2012, a set of wide ranging mobility surveys taken periodically as a joint initiative of the Department of Territorial Policy and Public Works of the Government of Catalonia and the Metropolitan Transport Authority of Barcelona, Spain. The aim of the surveys is to describe the mobility of the resident population in the Metropolitan Region of Barcelona. The survey is taken every year, employing a computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI) technique to interview a representative sample of the population, consisting of a total of 4,642 interviews in 2004 and 6,462 in 2012. Details were collected for every trip made by the interviewees the day prior to the interview. Besides providing information about their mobility and some of their socioeconomic characteristics, participants were also asked about their opinion on some relevant aspects of the transport system, such as stating their satisfaction on using their main transport mode, or asking them about the reasons behind their modal choice. This operation yielded data on mobility behaviours on weekdays and reported a total of 15,616 journeys for 2004 and 24,491 for 2012. When we focused only on mobility within the municipality of Barcelona - excluding the rest of the Barcelona Metropolitan Region - the total number of reported journeys was 4,805 for 2004 and 7,512 for 2012.

Mobility data provided by the surveys was complemented with additional data coming from the statistical yearbooks published by the Statistics Department of Barcelona City Council (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2015). Among the variables provided by this source were motorisation and accident rates and the number of registered vehicles per year.

Statistical Analysis

In order to assess the different aspects of motorcycle mobility, a three-step analysis was designed to examine (1) the recent trend of motorisation, (2) the most prominent socioeconomic and mobile predictors for both motorcycle ownership and motorcycle use, and (3) the subjective assessment of motorcycle driving.

To examine the most recent trends (1), a comparison between the state of the mobility in the city in 2004 and 2012 was conducted. In this first part, 2004 and 2012 values for selected variables such as number of registered vehicles, number of actual trips made

and number of trips made specifically by motorcycle, were compared. The study also provides an optic on the demographic structure of motorcycle trips to compare how the age and gender configuration of users has changed from one year to another.

The analysis of the significant predictors of modal choice (2) required of a two-step method consisting on a binary logistic regression model devoted to understand the drivers of motorbike ownership, followed by a multinomial logistic regression that focused on the drivers of motorcycle use for those who already had access to a motorbike. This step is focused only on the most recent 2012 data. The use of logit models to assess modal choice has a large tradition in transport studies, starting from the studies by McFadden (1974). The dependant variable in our Model 1 was the access to a motorbike (1=Yes and 0=No), and the set of explanatory variables was selected after testing for significance in bivariate Pearson χ^2 tests. The independent variables included demographic factors (Gender and Age) socioeconomic factors (Education level; Professional situation) and self reported habitual travel attitudes (Frequency of use of the car and Frequency of use of the public transport). For its part, Model 2 is devoted on understanding factors influencing modal choice of motorbike owners. The dependant variable in Model 2 is thus modal choice (1= Motorbike; 2=Non motorized/Public transport; 3 = Car) and takes motorbike as the reference category. The model aims specifically at whether motorbike owners actually use their motorbike on their daily trips. Among the selected variables included were demographic factors (*Gender* and *Age*) socioeconomic factors (*Education*) and travel related factors (*distance of the trip* and *trip purpose*). To screen selected independent variables for multicollinearity we analyzed zero-order correlations and variance inflation factors (VIF). No two variables in the regression model were unacceptably correlated, with all VIF factors within acceptable standards (mean VIF= 1.53). The complete set of explanatory variables used in both binary and multinomial models is found on table 1.

Table 1: Set of explanatory variables used in binary and multinomial models

Variable	Variables relative to the individual (used in model 1)		Variables relative to the trips (used in model 2)			Standard Deviation
	N	Column N %	N	Column N %	Mean	
<i>Gender</i>						
	Home	772 46,8%	2840	44,1%		
	Dona	877 53,2%	3592	55,9%		

<i>Age</i>					
	<= 30	388	23,5%	1411	21,9%
	31 - 45	624	37,8%	2591	40,3%
	46+	638	38,7%	2430	37,8%
<i>Education level</i>					
	None or primary	301	18,3%	1064	16,6%
	Secondary	572	34,8%	2295	35,8%
	College	772	46,9%	3049	47,6%
<i>Professional status</i>					
	Employed	1007	61,1%		
	Unemployed	285	17,3%		
	Retired/inactive	357	21,7%		
<i>Use of the car (self-reported)</i>					
	Never	911	55,2%		
	Occasional	553	33,6%		
	Always	185	11,2%		
<i>Use of the public transport (self-reported)</i>					
	Never	154	9,3%		
	Occasional	814	49,3%		
	Always	681	41,3%		
<i>Distance in Km (continuous)</i>				5,5	6,1
<i>Travel time (continuous)</i>				20.3	15.2
<i>Modal Choice</i>					
	Non-motorized/public			5079	79%
	Private: Car			912	14,2%
	Private: Motorbike			439	6,8%
<i>Trip purpose</i>					
	Work/study			1351	21,0%
	Shopping + Personal/family arrangements			1579	24,6%
	Leisure/social activities			789	12,3%
	Return home			2713	42,2%

Finally, to assess the subjective evaluation of motorcycling inside the city (3), we used descriptive statistics to compare how motorcyclists and car drivers rated their main use of transport, how they evaluated the inherent risk of driving, and found a different pattern of answers when trying to justify their modal choice. First the comparison was conducted upon the Satisfaction and Risk perception variables. Satisfaction ranked in a scale from 0 to 10, on how content were users with their main mode of transport, in a similar manner as Paviotti and Vogiatzis (2012). Similarly, participants were also asked what was their feeling of risk when using their mode of transport, creating a risk factor index that is similar to the danger score used by Shahar et al. (2010).

After that, the comparison between motorcycle/car users was conducted upon their stated reasons for using either a motorcycle or a car. Participants could state up to 3 different reasons in an open-ended question. Answers were later coded into a list that included operational, subjective and ideological reasons for using private transport. This type of data has already been used in other transport studies (Van Exel & Rietveld, 2009) to compare public transport and car users, but to the best of our knowledge, it is the first time that this kind of data is being used to describe motorcycle behaviour.

Analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS v19 and Stata v13.1.

4. Results

Assessing the situation of motorcycles in Barcelona

Over the last eight years Barcelona has seen an increase of two-wheeled motorized mobility with the number of motorcycles growing by 36.2% (Table 1). The motorisation rate has grown from 94.6 motorcycles per 1,000 inhabitants in 2004 to 136 in 2012. Two-wheeled vehicles represent 22.2% of all the motorised vehicles circulating in the city and the number of trips made in that mode of transport has grown to represent 26.5% of all motorised mobility. This growth has taken place in a context that is characterised by a clear drop in the rates of private motorised mobility, due to the economic crisis that started in 2008. Because of that, and as shown in Table 1, whereas the overall number of trips taken in Barcelona has increased by 16.1% between 2004 and 2012, the relative weight of the private modes of transport, has descended from 26.4% in 2004 to 21.1% in 2012. The main drop is caused by the fall in car usage (-14.5%) and not by motorcycle usage. In fact, motorcycle usage not only does not decrease, but instead it grows by 18.6%.

If we focus on the 372,278 trips that are made every day in the two-wheeled motorized modes of transport, we can see that the majority of them are performed by middle-aged people between 30 and 64 years of age (72.1%) and also mainly by men (68.8%). The trend between 2004 and 2012 has been clearly that of intensifying the role of middle-age in motorcycle riding (+31.8%), but this same period has also seen a significant increase in the ridership rates for women (+43.6%).

Table 2. Evolution of the use of the motorcycle in Barcelona for period 2004-2012.

Number of Registered Vehicles	2004	2012	2004-2012
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<i>Car</i>	607791 (71.4%)	584848 (60.4%)	-3,8%
<i>Motorcycle</i>	149363 (17.5%)	203414 (22.2%)	+36,2%
<i>All registered Vehicles</i>	851502 (100%)	968332 (100%)	+13.7%
Number of trips			
<i>Non motorized</i>	2008627 (34.8%)	2803244 (41.9%)	+39.6%
<i>Public Transport</i>	2133646 (37.0%)	2333748 (34.9%)	+9.4%
<i>Car</i>	1209955 (21.0%)	1034612 (15.5%)	-14.5%
<i>Motorcycle</i>	313779 (5.4%)	372278 (5.6%)	+18.6%
<i>All trips</i>	5765970 (100%)	6693909 (100%)	+16.1%
Motorcycle trips			
<i>Age 16-29</i>	105280 (33.6%)	99120 (26.6%)	-5.9%
<i>Age 30-64</i>	203544 (64.9%)	268372 (72.1%)	+31.8%
<i>Age 65+</i>	4955 (1.6%)	4785 (1.3%)	-3.4%
<i>All ages</i>	313779 (100.0%)	372278 (100.0%)	+18.6%
<i>Male</i>	232903 (74.2%)	256113 (68.8%)	+10.0%
<i>Female</i>	80877 (25.8%)	116164 (31.2%)	+43.6%
<i>All genders</i>	313779 (100.0%)	372278 (100.0%)	+18.6%

Source: Own production from EMEF 2004, 2012 and Barcelona City Council data

Explaining ridership as a modal choice

In attempting to understand which factors are behind this growth of two-wheeled mobility, it is necessary to analyse what are the demographic and trip-related factors that explain the modal decision for using the motorcycle. Due to the fact that using a motorbike is predated by the decision of whether or not to own a motorbike, Model 1 takes into account selected socioeconomic and travel attitude variables in order to determine the main determinants of motorbike ownership.

Model 1 on Table 3 show how some socioeconomic characteristics and attitudes towards transport clearly affect at the outcome of having or not a motorcycle. Results suggest that motorcycle ownership is in fact identified with young men (between 16-30) and it clearly fades as age grows. The odds of owning a two-wheeled vehicle are also higher among people with university studies and that are currently employed. Finally, results of the regression analysis also suggest that the most habitual users of car and public transport tend to show lower odds ratio of owning a motorbike. In fact motorbike owners are associated with using neither car nor public transport, which suggests a close

relationship between having access to a motorbike and actually using it on a day to day basis.

Table 3: Probability of having access to a motorcycle. Logistic regression analysis.

Independent Variables	B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95% C.I.for EXP(B)		Chi-Square
							Lower	Upper	
<i>Gender</i>									37.340**
Home									
Dona	-0.407	0.204	3.966	1	0.046	0.666	0.446	0.994	
<i>Age</i>									13.470**
<= 30			9.264	2	0.010				
31 - 45	-0.535	0.250	4.588	1	0.032	0.586	0.359	0.956	
46+	-0.792	0.263	9.050	1	0.003	0.453	0.270	0.759	
<i>Education level</i>									21.077**
None or primary			0.283	2	0.868				
Secondary	-0.065	0.311	0.044	1	0.833	0.937	0.509	1.723	
College	0.054	0.300	0.032	1	0.857	1.056	0.586	1.901	
<i>Professional status</i>									75.922**
Employed			26.311	2	0.000				
Unemployed	-0.852	.278	9.417	1	0.002	0.427	0.248	0.735	
Retired/inactive	-1.759	.375	22.029	1	0.000	0.172	0.083	0.359	
<i>Use of the car (self-reported)</i>									30.647**
Never			21.877	2	0.000				
Occasional	-0.028	.214	.017	1	0.897	0.973	0.639	1.481	
Always	-1.594	.363	19.276	1	0.000	0.203	0.100	0.414	
<i>Use of the public transport (self-reported)</i>									245.494**
Never			137.356	2	0.000				
Occasional	-2.063	.230	80.439	1	0.000	0.127	0.081	0.199	
Always	-3.762	.340	122.475	1	0.000	0.023	0.012	0.045	
Constant	1.017	.389	6.845	1	0.009	2.766			

Notes for the model: Rho-Square (Nagelkerke) = 0.293; -2Log likelihood = 779.175; Pseudo R² (Cox & Snell) = 0.135;

* $\alpha=0,05$

** $\alpha=0,001$

Source: Own production from EMEF 2012 data

The second part of the analysis was to focus on the trips made by those who had access to a motorbike to analyze whether having access to a two-wheeled vehicle actually affected their daily modal choice. In order to do so, model 3 aimed analyze the role of socioeconomic characteristics and travel related characteristics on the final modal decision of motorbike owners.

Table 4, has the relative risk of choosing the motorbike over the public transport or the non-motorized modes and also of choosing the motorbike over the car. Because the

coefficients of multinomial logistic models are generally difficult to interpret directly, marginal effects of each variable on each possible answer were computed in Table 5. Motorbike modal choice is positively associated with college educated people, with trips that require longer distances and with shorter trips in terms of travel time.

Table 4:

Model 2: Probability of using a motorbike as modal choice.

Modal choice (Motorbike=ref)	Coef	Std. Error	z	p	95% C.I. Higher	95% C.I. Lower
Non motorized/Public						
<i>Socioeconomic variables</i>						
Age	-0,006	0,014	-0,460	0,644	-0,034	0,021
Gender: Male	0.000					
Gender: Female	0,135	0,320	0,420	0,674	-0,493	0,763
Education: none/primary	0.000					
Education: Secondary	-0,659	0,468	-1,410	0,159	-1,575	0,257
Education: College	-1,673	0,441	-3,790	0,000	-2,537	-0,809
<i>Travel related variables</i>						
Distance	-2,799	0,282	-9,940	0,000	-3,351	-2,247
Travel time	1,143	0,124	9,260	0,000	0,901	1,385
Trip purpose: Work/study	-0,580	0,391	-1,480	0,138	-1,345	0,186
Trip purpose: Shopping + family arrangements	0,508	0,395	1,290	0,198	-0,267	1,283
Trip purpose: Leisure/social	-0,092	0,469	-0,200	0,844	-1,011	0,826
Trip purpose: Return home	0.000	.	.	-	.	.
Constant	-0,664	0,717	-0,930	0,354	-2,068	0,741
Car						
<i>Socioeconomic variables</i>						
Age	-0,014	0,015	-0,890	0,371	-0,044	0,016
Gender: Male	0.000					
Gender: Female	-1,006	0,383	-2,620	0,009	-1,756	-0,255
Education: none/primary	0.000					
Education: Secondary	-0,677	0,520	-1,300	0,193	-1,696	0,341
Education: College	-0,911	0,480	-1,900	0,048	-1,853	0,030
<i>Travel related variables</i>						
Distance	-2,406	0,284	-8,460	0,000	-2,963	-1,849
Travel time	1,060	0,124	8,530	0,000	0,817	1,304
Trip purpose: Work/study	-0,367	0,407	-0,900	0,367	-1,165	0,431
Trip purpose: Shopping + family arrangements	0,438	0,447	0,980	0,327	-0,438	1,314
Trip purpose: Leisure/social	0,565	0,467	1,210	0,226	-0,349	1,480
Trip purpose: Return home	0.000					
Constant	-1,945	0,807	-2,410	0,016	-3,526	-0,364
Log-likelihood: 315.022; Pseudo R2: 0.4417						

Source: Own production from EMEF 2012 data

Choosing not to use the motorbike and rather use non motorized modes of transport or public transport was slightly associated with being female and longer travel times, at the same time that was negatively associated with college education and trip distance. Finally, choosing not to use the motorbike to use the car instead was associated with longer travel times and negatively associated with being female. At this stage of the analysis is also remarkable how trip purpose was not found significant at determining modal choice, denoting a notable disassociation between purpose and modal selection among motorbike users.

Table 4: Estimated marginal effects on the probability of modal choice among people with Access to the motorbike.

	Motorbike		Non motorized/Public		Car	
	dy/dx	p	dy/dx	p	dy/dx	p
Socioeconomic variables						
Age	0,001	0,441	0,000	0,991	-0,001	0,443
Gender: Female	0,029	0,284	0,058	0,041*	-0,087	0,000**
Education: Secondary	0,084	0,130	-0,052	0,335	-0,032	0,471
Education: College	0,152	0,003*	-0,145	0,004*	-0,006	0,884
Travel related variables						
Distance	0,256	0,000**	-0,171	0,000**	-0,085	0,000**
Travel time	-0,108	0,000**	0,066	0,000**	0,042	0,000**
Trip purpose: Work/study	0,045	0,138	-0,040	0,240	-0,005	0,865
Trip purpose: Shopping + family arrangements	-0,053	0,204	0,036	0,356	0,017	0,649
Trip purpose: Leisure/social	-0,025	0,589	-0,038	0,347	0,063	0,144

Note: dy/dx = percent increase in probability of outcome due to variable.

* $\alpha=0,05$ ** $\alpha=0,001$

Source: Own production from EMEF 2012 data

Subjective evaluation of ridership

Table 5 shows, on a scale from one to ten, how car and motorcycle users evaluate their satisfaction on using their main mode of transport, along with how they perceive the possibility of having an accident during their trip. Motorcycle users are those that evaluate their mode of transport higher, the average mark being (8.12 out of 10) in comparison with that of public transport users (7.09) and car drivers (6.97). On average, motorbike users are 1.16 points more satisfied than car users. As the frequency of motorbike use increases it also increases the average satisfaction. By contrast, most frequent car users show less satisfaction than occasional users.

On the other hand, motorcyclists are also the ones assessing a higher insecurity, 1.47 times higher than drivers. It is also interesting to see that as the frequency of motorcycle use increases the fear or insecurity factor decreases almost at the same rate. As explained by Broughton et al. (2009) the reduction in the fear factor can be explained either by an overestimation of the rider’s capability or by an underestimation of the task demands of riding a motorcycle. Car users appear to be less aware of the inherent risk of driving, although their risk assessment is more stable around the average than that of motorcyclists.

Table 5: Subjective assessment of satisfaction/fear levels on motorcyclists and car drivers.

	Motorcycle		Car		Difference Moto/Car	
	Satisfaction (over 10)	Fear (over 10)	Satisfaction (over 10)	Fear (over 10)	Satisfaction	Fear
All users	8.12	5.45	6.97	3.70	1.16	1.47
“Occasional / rare”	7.86	5.82	6.75	3.75	1.16	1.56
“Frequently”	8.40	5.57	7.48	3.37	1.12	1.65
“Always”	8.66	5.15	7.19	3.73	1.21	1.38

Source: Own production from EMEF 2012 data

To understand why motorcycle users are more satisfied than car users or public transport users, it is important to analyse what are the reasons for which they choose the motorcycle in their daily mobility. Comparing motorcyclist answers with car driver answers also helps to give a glimpse of the hidden rationalities behind each mode of transport. As shown in Table 5, car and motorcycle users endorse very different statements when they are asked about the main reasons for using private transport. Firstly, motorcyclists were more prolific at rationalising their travel behaviour, as they submitted an average of two reasons on the survey. In contrast, car drivers submitted an average of 0.9 answers. Of all the answers submitted by motorcyclists, 35.3% were to point out that using the motorcycle was “faster than public transport”, “more comfortable” (23.3%) and “cheaper than public transport” (14.6%). Car users agreed both on the speed issue (21.9%) and the comfort (28.8%), but the monetary cost was clearly not a factor for them (4.7%).

Table 5: Endorsement of statements for using motorcycle/car

Why do you use motorcycle/car?	Motorcycle users	Car users	Odds Ratio
Is cheaper than public transport	14,6%	4,7%	3,44
Is faster than public transport	35,3%	21,9%	1,94
Easy parking	4,3%	2,2%	1,99
It is more comfortable	23,3%	28,8%	0,75
It gives me more freedom	10,1%	4,3%	2,49
I have no other option	0,3%	4,8%	0,07
I prefer private over public transport	3,0%	2,4%	1,26
Lack of public transport alternative/info	4,1%	13,0%	0,29
Complexity of the route	4,1%	2,8%	1,50
They drive me	0,9%	15,1%	0,05
Total	100,0%	100,0%	

Comments: The question was: Why do you use motorcycle/car to move instead of using public transport. The question was open ended and the answers were recoded into the present list.

Source: Own production from EMEF 2012 data

Even more interesting is looking at those answers that were more typical of motorcycle users in comparison with those answers given by car drivers. Motorcyclists were 3.44 times more likely to rationalise their use of the motorcycle, because of the price factor, and 2.49 times to rationalise it because of the freedom that the motorcycle gave them. Parking availability is also an important factor for motorcycle users, as the operational speeds of the motorcycle were also strong reasons that were linked with motorcycle use. In contrast, answers such as “others drive me”, “I have no other option” or even “it is more comfortable” were much more related with car drivers. In sum, motorcycle use is characterised by a set of operational factors such as price, speed and parking availability, but also some subjective factors such as perceived freedom and ideology. Finally, having complex routes can also promote motorcycle use.

5. Discussion

The unprecedented rise in the number of motorcycles in Barcelona has both political and mobility causes. On the one hand, the 2004 reform opened the possibility of switching from car use to motorcycle use for a large group of people who were typically using their car for intra-city, short-distance travelling. Those new clients of the motorcycle were middle-aged men and women (30-64 years) who probably saw in the motorcycle a cheap and satisfying way of escaping from the car gridlock without having to abandon the dynamism of personal motorised transport.

Results of the binary and multinomial logistic models have proven that motorbike users have a highly defined sociodemographic profile. In absolute terms, the most usual

profile of the motorcycle user in Barcelona is that of an employed young man. These same socioeconomic features also are associated with not only owning a motorbike but actually using it before any other mode of transport. Whereas motorcycling is a clearly gendered activity -both the decision of having one and the decision of using it-, the rate of women's motorcycle utilisation is three times higher in Barcelona than the rate reported by Kopp (2011) for Paris and it is also higher than the rate reported by Fuentes et al. (2010) for less-urbanised areas of Catalonia.

Results confirm Kopp's (2011) hypothesis that motorbike use in European cities is mainly affected by age and gender. Results however, also show that employment status, is also associated with higher motorbike ownership, at the same time that education level is associated with a higher frequency of motorbike use, among those who already have access to a two-wheeled vehicle, especially for those with a college degree. In our opinion, the predictive value of the education level and professional situation can somehow be related with income. The decision on actually owning a motorbike appears to depend more on professional situation than on education level, when we analyze the actual modal choice of motorbike owners, education level is a strong predictor for motorbike use. This might suggest that motorbike ownership and actual use in European cities is situated in a middle-ground amid what Dargay (2001) described as a strong relation between motorization rates and economic status and what is found in South-east Asia and some developing countries, where motorbike ownership is strictly related with low income and low-status groups of population (Jou & Chen, 2014).

However, the fact that motorcycle use has been continuously rising, even in a context of deep economic crisis, can also be linked with the hypothesis of Pinch and Reimers (2012) upon which the two key factors that shape motorcycle mobility over time are affordability and manoeuvrability. This idea is also consistent with the global dynamic for motorcycle ownership described by Nishitatenno and Burke (2014). In the specific case of Barcelona, motorbike sales during period 2004-2008 might have been driven by operational factors such as speed and dynamism that made the motorcycle an attractive mode of transport in a dense city. In contrast, during period 2008-2012, the affordability factor might have taken the lead at explaining why motorcycle sales have maintained their pace while car sales have dropped dramatically. The fact that the economic factor is stated as the third most given answer to the question "Why do you use the motorcycle?" reinforces the strength of the affordability hypothesis. However, the

affordability factor cannot be viewed as only a matter of the cost of the vehicle, but also the recurrent costs associated with its use in the context of a compact city. Shorter travel times entail less fuel consumption and free parking on the street means having to spend less time in private parking spots. It is this added sum of costs, which explain that motorcyclists are 3.44 more prone to justifying their use of the motorcycle by the economic factor. Thus, it is possible to conclude that despite the fact that motorcycle use is not, by any means, a mode of transport associated with low-class or low-income status, the affordability of the motorcycle when compared with the car does indeed explain the growing share of motorcycle use in the city.

Notwithstanding, whereas the affordability factor can explain the growing trend in large numbers, the results of the logistic models confirm Kopp's (2011) observation that motorcycle ownership is mainly determined by age and gender, rather than income or other socioeconomic factors. At the same time, our study also confirms that motorcycle use is independent from trip purpose. Motorbike use appears to be equally associated with occupational and personal mobility, and at the same time our study differs from Broughton et al. (2009), who consider motorcycle use in terms of leisure activity and placed status over functionality. This disassociation between travel purpose and motorbike use has important consequences in terms of transport policies, as measures aimed at regulating motorbike ownership can be more successful than policies aimed towards regulating motorbike use. Finally, the fact that women are less likely to use the motorbike than men even when they have equal access to it contributes to explain the gendered general mobility habits in urban areas (Miralles-Guasch, Martinez Melo, & Marquet, 2016).

On the subjective dimension of the analysis, it is noteworthy how motorcycle users are fully aware of the inherent risk of their modal choice. In fact, and again differing from the results of research by Broughton et al. (2009), riders showed a higher risk awareness than drivers. This risk however is rationalised by the most frequent motorcycle users. This self-confidence of the riders may also help to explain the difficulty of reducing motorcycle accidents. Between 2004 and 2012 the city has been able to diminish the ratio of car accidents by 20%, in comparison with the low 1.5% reduction of motorbike accidents (Ajuntament de Barcelona, 2015). This is consistent with what Jamson and Chorlton (2009) observed for the UK, where controlling for motorcycle accidents also proves to be harder than for cars. It also confirms the Lin and Kraus (2009) hypothesis

on which over-confidence in one's driving abilities contributes to higher accident rates. The stark increase in the number of actual motorists that followed the 2004 policy reform also caused an increase in the number of accidents due to the fact that novice drivers are more prone to having accidents than experienced ones (Hosking, Liu, & Bayly, 2010; Shahar et al., 2010).

The fact that the rationalities behind the motorcyclists and drivers are so differentiated shows that motorcycle use is not being considered by the same standards as other forms of private transport. Thus, it should be given proper attention as a singular form of transport that is answering driver's needs that are specific and unique. In sum, motorcycle use is characterised by a set of functional factors such as price, speed and parking availability, but also by some subjective factors such as perceived freedom and preference over other modes of transport. Together, objective and subjective factors affect the whole three stages of private transport: modal choice, journey and parking (Miralles-Guasch, Martinez-Melo, & Marquet Sarda, 2014). Motorcycles are attractive because they are objectively cheaper than cars and faster at covering distances inside dense urban environments (Broughton et al., 2009). But, with respect to the findings of Jamson and Chorlton (2009), the analysis of the self-reported evaluation of riding also points to the fact that there are some important subjective factors boosting the attraction of the motorcycle. Driving in a dense and compact city such as Barcelona provides a dynamic experience for motorcycle riders, much in contrast with the static experience for car drivers. It is not just the objective shorter travel times, but also the pleasant experience of the free-flow movement between cars (Mokhtarian, Papon, Goulard, & Diana 2014). Additionally, the facility of parking at destination eases the burden of seeking parking, which is usually associated with negative perceptions of motorised transport (Beirão & Sarsfield Cabral, 2007; Ducreux, 2008; Miralles-Guasch et al., 2014).

Our study empirically confirms the hypothesis of Nishitateno and Burke (2014) that motorcycle use follows a complex trade-off between three fundamental factors: affordability, risk and comfort. Understanding the inner mechanisms of these tradeoffs however, will require further analysis, plus it will also be necessary to fully understand why motorcycle use is still deeply gendered. Furthermore, seeing two-wheeled motorized mobility either as a solution to urban congestion for dense cities or as a further threat to urban sustainability will depend, in part to whether new motorbikers are

essentially former car drivers or former public transport/non motorized users. This is important because even if we were to see motorbike as a more efficient mode of transport –i.e. less pollution, less space occupied, better average speeds and less congestion overall- we would still have to cope with additional challenges inherent to private motorized modes of transport such as social disadvantage due to a unequal access, the noise pollution and a alarmingly high accident rates. Achieving this next step of research would provide public managers with additional arguments to implement specific policies oriented towards the two-wheeled mobility, either to promote it or dissuade it.

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